
Online Transportation Supply Chain On Service Quality, Price, And Trust In Consumer Satisfaction In The Covid 19 Pandemic

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ABSTRACT

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Development of technology causes a variety of changes for humans. All things can be identified quickly and transparently by technology. Technology also provides humans a lot of convenience in carrying out activities. Transportation can move quickly and play a significant role in our life. This study aimed to determine the effect of service quality, price, consumer trust in online transportation on consumer satisfaction during the Covid-19 Pandemic. This study used Path analysis. The samples used as units of analysis were 100 Medan City people using online transportation applications. Besides, this study employed accidental sampling. The results of the study were service quality had a significant effect on price; the price had a significant effect on customer satisfaction; the trust has a significant impact on customer satisfaction; the quality of service affected customer satisfaction through price and customer trust

1. INTRODUCTION

The inevitable technological advances in everyday life cause humans to need service providers who provide better and innovative services. Companies can create, build, and manage innovation through customer satisfaction by improving service performance (Mohammed et al., 2017). Along with the rapid development of technology in the current era of globalization, technology has a positive impact on humans. Individuals personally have diverse activities so that they must be able to keep up with the changing times and technological advancements to survive. The development of technology causes a variety of changes for humans. All things can be identified quickly and transparently by technology. Technology also provides humans a lot of convenience in doing activities.

Transportation can move quickly and play a significant role in our lives. Over time, technology has made transportation more comfortable to move from one place to another, using online transportation. Current technology makes it easy for us to order transportation services online through the application. The simplicity of giving the application and the speed of travel time are the main highlights of choosing online transportation.

Apart from that, online transportation also brings a large number of advantages that everyone needs to find. The first advantage is safety. Online transportation is more superior compared to conventional transportation because consumers can feel safe when using online transportation services.

The presence of online transportation in Indonesia causes our economic growth to get better. The unemployment rate has been proven to decrease because of online transportation. Data from the Central Statistics Beaucracy showed economic growth in the third quarter of 2016, which reached 5.02%, with a decrease of 530,000 open unemployment rate to 7,030,000 people. The online transportation business also provides income that is higher than the minimum wage in the region. Online transportation becomes a tool to meet human needs and carry out their activities. Online transportation has a vital role in people's lives; it is often used to accelerate in achieving community goals. Online transportation services have become an essential thing to support the community in carrying out their daily activities as well. Today's consumers need online transportation that is fast, convenient, safe, and easy to find. The driving force for people to use technology in online transportation is online transportation has quality

standards, tariffs, and other things that can make someone trust in using online transportation. Several factors influence the use of online transportation, such as service quality, price, trust, and customer satisfaction. Expectations of higher quality market segment services affect the quality of lower market segments (Gnanlet & Yayla-Kullu, 2013).

Service quality has a significant and positive effect on customer satisfaction and business performance. The existence of customer satisfaction can be an intervention variable between business performance and quality. The mediating effect showed by customer satisfaction is partial mediation (Nurbismi & Gunawan, 2019). Service Quality plays an essential role for the company in the form of a perceived benefit based on customer evaluation of interaction compared to the expected benefits before. Service quality adds new empirical evidence of direct and indirect relationships between service quality, engagement, and customer satisfaction (Rasidah et al., 2018). In each criterion to determine the relative quality of service to each other, it has been found that the three best aspects of online transportation services are cognitive, perceived convenience, and website innovation. Meanwhile, the three lowest criteria are compensation, trust, and perceived risk (Silalahi et al., 2017). The seven dimensions of service quality (accessible, compatible services, service effectiveness, service efficiency, reliable services, providing appropriate services, and staff competency) take the model employed. Then, the users' perceptions were analyzed and compared. Service quality requirements were classified into five canoe classifications - interesting, must-be, one-dimensional, indifferent, and questionable/vice versa. Service quality was categorized in 'Indifferent' (Taib et al., 2018). The classification of canoe-interesting classification services means providing services from the company to facilitate consumers to receive the services provided. Consumers must be prioritized and well served. If these consumers can benefit the company, the company can continue to develop. The service quality can be assessed by comparing consumer perceptions of services received from the company. (Zaini et al., 2020). Service quality directly contributes to maintaining strong and loyal relationships between customers and online transportation. In the context of customer satisfaction, online transportation has been able to meet the expectations of the customer. However, there are still a few items that need to be fixed in

online transportation (Saputra & Hati, 2019). The service quality at the online transportation company is still unsatisfactory because there are still consumer complaints, and the company does not respond so that those consumers provide a review and comment directly to the application (Pujiah & Fatmawati, 2018). Partially and simultaneously, the dimensions of service quality (reliability, direct evidence, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy) provided by online transportation services have a positive and significant effect (Indrawati, 2011). Price is an exchange rate that can be equated with money or other goods for the benefits obtained from an item or service for a person or group at a particular time and place (Isfahila et al., 2018). The high and low prices can be determined by the demand and supply in the market. If the offered price is by the benefits received by consumers, online transportation will use the service repeatedly and vice versa (Isfahila et al., 2018). In general, the price of a service is one influential factor because it can determine market demand. Price, which can be defined as "something that is spent by the consumer or customer in the form of money to pay for the services," at this online transportation company, is affordable from the type of fleet offered; consumers are free to choose what kind of fleet you want to use (Maulana, 2016). In addition to service quality and price, consumer trust also plays a significant role in a company. Only customers who have trust will dare to make transactions through the internet application media. Without customers' trust, an online transportation transaction cannot occur. Consumer trust to have a transaction with online transportation will increase when online transportation vendors provide several things supporting the transaction process because consumers will be more careful in choosing transportation (Novitasari & Suryani, 2019). Consumer trust is all about consumers' knowledge. Consumer trust must be maintained and enhanced for the development of the company; more efforts are needed to obtain, maintain, and increase consumer trust (Maharama & Kholis, 2018). Trust in the sales force influences trust in the supplier company. This trust, which will later influence consumer purchase intentions and the continued relationship with suppliers, can increase the number of purchases in the online industry, which has created trust as a critical path in an online environment. Trust has been identified as crucial in online trading. Consumers are reluctant to have purchase intentions when online transportation distrusts the website. Today's consumers, who

represent prospective buyers, seem to have reasons why online transportation can trust online trade and ultimately lead online transportation to have purchase intentions (Makmor et al., 2018). Two parties involved in a trust relationship can be individuals or groups, such as organizations. Research has shown that trust is the key to understanding social relationships, as well as people's attitudes and behavior in situations where uncertainty and/or risk is felt (Li, 2014). Morling and Strannegard stated that the popularity and trust in online transportation could give a sense of prestige and pride to consumers. Therefore, popularity and trust are the first and foremost thing considered by consumers to have the intention to buy a service. Price, service quality, and trust simultaneously have a significant effect on customer satisfaction to online transportation (Adji, 2014). The practical implication that needs to be taken into account by service providers in the provision of competent service quality, such as paying attention to cleanliness and tidiness of transport, providing responsive service responses with the right time of attendance accompanied by increased driver ability

(Kavitha & Rapoor, 2019). Also, customer trust needs to be maintained by providing comfort, satisfaction, and responsible services (Pasharibu et al., 2018). Therefore, consumer trust in the company includes how the company behaves like honesty, consistency, and responsibility.

Consumer satisfaction is someone's feeling of pleasure or disappointment of someone as the result of a comparison of the perception of service performance and expectations. In general, if a consumer is satisfied with the service, the consumer will use the service continuously. Each consumer satisfaction must always be prioritized because it affects the use of a service. The better the service quality, customer satisfaction with the company will be higher. Problems of consumer satisfaction will arise if one factor is not met. Therefore, based on the factors listed above, consumer satisfaction to online transportation can be seen if the service quality is getting better, the price is also relatively affordable for all people, and there is a guarantee that can make consumers have a sense of trust to use the services of this online transportation company. Interest can also arise due to customer satisfaction with service quality, price, and trust in services are used repeatedly.

The existence of smartphone information technology that can download online transportation

services through online applications now greatly facilitates the activity of traveling anywhere with a fixed price system without any price increases even in a state of traffic jams or weather changing badly when the trip is being made from one place to another place to support the interests of the public to download online transportation services applications online or try to use online transportation services regularly and repeatedly. Common online transportation modes can be obtained by using smartphone technology, having an online transportation mode application. Modes of online transportation available in the city of Medan consist of: Go-Jek, which consists of Go-Ride, Go-Send, Go-Mart, Go-Food, Go-Box, GoClean, Go-Glam, Go-Massage, and Go-Busway; online Grab online transportation, which consists of Grab-Car, Grab-Ride, Grab-Send, Grab-Food, and the latest In-Driver online transportation. All online transportations use location-based search applications for mobile phones based on Android and iOS. From these applications, online transportation drivers can view incoming orders and the location of their customers to respond to, and customers can monitor the position of online transportation drivers who respond to their orders.

Online transportation has been operated in the areas of Medan, Greater Jakarta, Surabaya, Bali, Yogyakarta, Makassar, and Balikpapan. Online transportation service develops not only as online transportation of people, but also can be used as the delivery of goods, documents, or packages, even as the delivery of ordered food. Based on the results of interviews, the service quality, prices, and consumer trust in online transportation companies are still lacking, causing many loyal users of online transportation from 2015-2019 to still provided complaints and input so that online transportation companies could continue to grow and provide better innovations. During the Covid-19 pandemic, the need for online transportation is in high demand, resulting in intense competition. However, as the spread of Covid-19 has caused many regulations issued by the Government to break the virus distribution chain, this case has caused consumers to be more careful about the existence of online transportation. Therefore, this study aimed to find out the effect of service quality, price, consumer trust in online transportation to consumer satisfaction during the Covid-19 Pandemic. Based on the results of the above background description, the authors are interested in conducting a study entitled "Service Quality,

2. LITERARY REVIEW

2.1 Service Quality

The concept of quality is considered as a standard of the perfection of a service, which consists of design quality and conformance quality. The design quality is a specific function of a service, while the quality of conformity is a standard of how much the level of conformity between service with quality requirements or specifications previously set (Tjiptono & Chandra, 2011). Gummesson stated that service quality could be identified from consumers' perceptions of the services received by online transportation so that the service has its value for customers concerning creating customer values (Tjiptono & Chandra, 2004, 2011). Service quality is one essential element taken into account by customers in purchasing a service (Kavitha & Rapoor, 2019). Five dimensions in service quality are tangible (direct evidence), reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy (Empathy) (Tjiptono & Chandra, 2011).

2.2 Price

Price is the amount of money billed for a service, or the amount of value exchanged by customers to obtain the benefits of owning or using a service (Kotler & Keller, 2013). Price is significant in marketing service because the price is one of the four marketing mixes (service, price, place, promotion). Price is an exchange rate of goods and services stated in monetary units, and also one of the determinants of the company success because the price determines how much profit the company will attain from the sale of goods or services (Kotler & Keller, 2013). Four indicators that characterize prices are affordability, competitiveness, suitability with service quality, and suitability with service benefits (Armstrong et al., 2009).

2.3 Trust

Trust is a fundamental element of building a relationship quality model in which a person's willingness relies on others where we believe in them (Putri & Sudiksa, 2018). Trust is a mental condition based on a person's

situation and social context. When a person makes a decision, he will choose decisions based on the choices of people he can trust more than the less trusted ones. The indicators of trust are benevolence, integrity, competence, willingness to depend, and the subjective probability of dependent (Veno & Subagio, 2013)

2.4 Customer Satisfaction

Satisfaction is the level of a person's feelings after comparing the performance or results to their expectations (Mowen & Minor, 2002). Satisfaction is the level of how much a customer's needs and desires are met by the service used (Achrol & Kotler, 2012). The indicators are complaints and suggestions system, ghost shopping, lost customer analysis, and survey on customer satisfaction (Du et al., 2010).

3 RESEARCH METHOD

3.1 Type of Research

This research is quantitative descriptive research to examine the relationship between the effect of service quality, price, and trust on consumer satisfaction with the help of the SPSS 24 program.

3.2 Research Object

Research objects involved in this research were consumer users of online transportation applications in Medan City.

3.3 Population and Sample

The population in this study was 2 210 624 people (Medan Central Statistics Beauracracy, 2019). The samples were used as a unit of analysis as the Medan citizens who used online transportation applications in this study were 100 people. This study employed accidental sampling. The number of samples was determined using the Slovin formula, with an error percentage of 10%.

3.4 Operational Definition of Variables

The operational definitions of the research variables are as follows. Service Quality (X1) is the overall characteristics of an item or service that

influencing its ability to satisfy expressed or implied needs. The indicators are Tangible (direct evidence), reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy. Price is an exchange rate of goods and services expressed in monetary units and also is one of the determinants of the company's success because the price determines how much profit the company will obtain from the sale of goods or services. The indicators are affordability, competitiveness, conformity with service quality. Trust is a mental condition based on a person's situation and social context. When someone makes a decision, he will prefer decisions based on the choices of people he can trust more than the less trusted ones. The indicators are benevolence, integrity, competence, willingness to depend on, the subjective probability of depending. Trust is the level of one's feelings after comparing the performance or results to his expectations. The

indicators are complaints and suggestions system, ghost shopping, lost customer analysis, and survey on customer satisfaction.

3.5 Analysis Method

This study used path analysis technique. The statistical hypothesis formulation model of path analysis is as follows:

$$X_2 = \beta_1 X_1 + e_1$$

$$Y = \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + e_2$$

$$X_3 = \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + e_3$$

Notes :

Y: Trust

β : Regression coefficient that would be tested

X1: Service quality

X2: Price

X3: Trust

e: Error standard

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Path Analysis

The results of structural equation 1 are presented in the following table:

Table 1 Results of Structural Equation 1

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	4.121	.630		8.286	.000
H	.438	.226	.535	4.161	.063

Source : Research Finding (2020)

$$X_2 = 0.535X_1 + e_1$$

$$\beta_1 = 0.535$$

The β_1 value showed 0.535, which indicated a positive regression coefficient. This case showed direct change between service quality variable (X1) and price (X2), meaning that if the service quality (X1) increased by one unit, the price (X2) would

increase by 0.535 units. The value of $e_1 = 0.984$ as the error level for structural equation 1.

The results of structural equation 2 are presented in the following table

:

Table 2. Results of Structural Equation 2

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	.656	.543		3.221	.063
KP	.376	.054	.377	5.634	.000
H	.349	.076	.387	5.364	.000
Kep	.354	.065	.435	4.267	.000

Source : Research Finding (2020)

$$Y = 0.377 X_1 + 0.387 X_2 + 0.435 X_3 + e_2$$

$\beta_1 = 0.377$

The β_1 value showed 0.377, which indicated a positive regression coefficient. It shows a direct change between the service quality (X1) variable and trust (Y) variable, meaning that if the service quality (X1) increased by one unit, then (Y) would 0.377 units by assuming the variables X2, X3 was constant.

$\beta_2 = 0.387$

The β_2 value showed 0.387, which indicated a positive regression coefficient. It showed a direct change between the price (X2) and customer satisfaction (Y), meaning that if the price (X2) increased by one unit, then the trust (Y) would

increase by 0.387 units by assuming the variables X1 and X3 were constant.

$\beta_3 = 0.435$

The β_3 value showed 0.435, which indicated a positive regression coefficient. It showed a direct change between the trust (X3) and customer satisfaction (Y), meaning that if the trust (X3) increased by one unit, then customer satisfaction (Y) would increase by 0.435 units by assuming the variables X1 and X2 were constant. $e_2 = 0.678$ as the error level for structural equation 2.

The results of structural equation 3 are presented in the following table:

Table 3 Results of Structural Equation 3

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	3.172	.573		6.480	.000
PK	.504	.402	.357	4.102	.049
KM	.505	.196	.361	4.537	.036

Source : Research Finding (2020)

$X_3 = 0.357 X_1 + 0.361 X_2 + e_3$

$\beta_1 = 0.357$

The β_1 value showed 0.357, which indicated a positive regression coefficient. It showed a direct change between service quality (X1) and customer satisfaction (Y), meaning that if the service quality (X1) increased by one unit, then the customer (Y) would increase by 0.357 units by assuming X2 variable was in a fixed or constant condition.

The β_2 value showed 0.361, which indicated a positive regression coefficient. It showed a direct change between the price (X2) and customer satisfaction (Y), meaning that if the price (X2) increased by one unit, then customer satisfaction (Y) would increase by 0.361 units by assuming variable X1 was constant.

$e_3 = 0.936$ as the error level for structural equation 3.

$\beta_2 = 0.361$

4.2 Interpretation of path analysis is as follows:

Table 4 Interpretation of Path Analysis

Direct effect	The effect of service quality on customer satisfaction	0.377
Indirect effect	1. Service quality directed to price and then to customer satisfaction.	$0.535 \times 0.387 = 0.207$
	2. Service quality directed to price and then to customer satisfaction, and customer satisfaction.	$0.535 \times 0.361 \times 0.435 = 0.084$
	3. Service quality directed to trust and then to customer satisfaction.	$0.357 \times 0.435 = 0.155$
	4.	
Total of effects	Direct effect + Indirect effects	$0.377 + 0.207 + 0.084 + 0.155 = 0.823$

Based on the calculation results of Table 4, the total effect value (0.823) > the value of the direct effect (0.377). This result indicated the direct effect of service quality on customer satisfaction was 0.377. Besides, the total effects of service quality on customer satisfaction through price and trustworthiness was 0.823. Then, there was an intervening/mediation relationship. It detected partial mediation because the value of service quality effect on customer satisfaction was not equal to zero by entering the price and customer satisfaction variables. This case means that the service quality must be through the price and trust variables first to influence customer satisfaction.

4.3 T-Test of Hypothesis

Based on calculations using the SPSS 24.0 program for windows, the researchers summarize the results of the t-test calculation as follows:

4.3.1 The Effect of Service Quality on Price

Based on the above table, the significance t value of service quality variable is 0.043, which is smaller than 0.05. This result indicated that the service quality had a significant effect on price. The results of the t-test calculations are presented in the following table:

Table 5 Results of t-test analysis

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	4.191	.730		8.286	.000
KP	.538	.416	.345	4.161	.043

4.3.2 The Effect of Price on Customer Satisfaction

Based on the above table, the significance value of

the price variable is 0.003, which is smaller than 0.05. This result indicated that the price had a significant effect on customer satisfaction. The results of the t-test calculations are presented in Table 6 are as follows:

Table 6 Results of t-test analysis

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	3.250	.622		7.340	.000
H	.528	.125	.580	5.206	.003

4.3.3 The Effect of Trust on Customer Satisfaction

Based on the above table, the significance value of the trust variable is 0.002, which is smaller than 0.05. This result indicated that trust had a significant effect on customer satisfaction. The results of the t-test

Table 7 Results of t-test analysis

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	3.236	.338		8.583	.000
Kep	.527	.128	.621	6.116	.002

Source : Research Finding (2020)

4.3.4 Analysis of the Effect of Service Quality on Price

From the test results, the service quality variable significantly influenced the price. This case can be seen from the significance value of $0.043 < 0.05$. This result showed that the service quality was related to the level of service to consumers obtain, so the consumers could understand and think that would show a sense of trust in online transportation. Service quality for online transportation is mainly related to service drivers. If consumers understand the quality of online transportation services, then the company offers can be easily assessed by consumers, and companies can quickly sell services based on service quality because the online transportation services have very good quality.

4.3.5 Analysis of the Effect of Price on Customer Satisfaction

The test results of tests showed that the price variable had a significant effect on customer satisfaction. This case can be seen from the significance value of $0.003 < 0.05$. Customer satisfaction would lead to a sense of satisfaction if the online transportation service company could maintain satisfaction from consumers, such as maintaining the quality provided and good service methods, consumers would feel satisfied. These ways would enable consumers to feel satisfied and have trust in the company so that the company obtains the benefits.

4.3.6 Analysis of the Effect of Trust on Customer Satisfaction

The test results showed that the trust variable had a significant effect on customer satisfaction. This case can be seen from the significance value of $0.002 < 0.05$. This result indicated that trust is a key indicator to make customers loyal in the long run and a determinant of long-term business. Customers who believe in online transportation services will feel happy and even continually use online transportation services

4.3.7 Analysis of Service Quality on Customer Satisfaction through Price and Customer Satisfaction

The test results showed that the service quality variable affected customer satisfaction through price and customer satisfaction. It can be seen from the value of total effects (0.823) > value of direct effect (0.377). This result confirmed that the effect of service on quality customer satisfaction must be

through price and trust so that if consumers can find out what is in this online transportation service by the promotion, they can foster trust in online transportation. Besides, if consumers expectation turns out to be more than the hope in online transportation services, they will feel satisfied and be loyal to online transportation services. Online transportation companies must be able to maintain quality and service because, from the results of the field survey, most consumers thought that if there were some components in the service which were not strong enough, the company must improve to keep the customers to remain in service. Although in the Covid-19 pandemic, it turns out that service quality, price, and trust in customer satisfaction are still expected by consumers who use online transportation.

5 CONCLUSION

The analysis results both descriptively and statistically concluded that service quality had a significant effect on prices; the price had a significant effect on customer satisfaction; the trust had a significant effect on customer satisfaction, and service quality affected customer satisfaction through price and customer trust. In this study, there were limitations in the questionnaire that were not understood by respondents, but this problem could be overcome.

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